

Factors Affecting Learners' Academic Performance

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ABSTRACT

Academic performance plays a crucial role in the students' overall development and success in their educational journey. However, there are many factors, such as learning environment, learning resources, family support, delivery of instructions, and study habits, that have influenced students' academic performance. The key purpose of this study is to find out the factors affecting learners' academic performance in one of the public elementary schools in a large-sized division in central Philippines for the school year 2025-2026 as the basis for an intervention plan. Descriptive research was conducted, and a 35-item survey questionnaire was used as a tool to gather data from seventy (70) learners. The results revealed that most of the respondents were 11-year-old grade 4 female learners with parents with lower educational backgrounds and belonged to higher-income families. Overall, the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance across areas was high. When grouped according to five profile variables, the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance was also high. Additionally, a significant difference was found in the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance related to learning resources when comparing different grade levels. This calls for school heads, teachers, and parents to work together to provide the learners the materials and support they need for their successful educational journey.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Classroom Environment, Learning Resources, Family Support, Study Habits

How to Cite:

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INTRODUCTION

Academic performance plays a crucial role in the students' overall development and success in their educational journey. It considers the ability to apply acquired knowledge and skills in various contexts. Additionally, when effective learning occurs, pupils are likely to achieve high academic performance (Narad and Abdullah, 2016). A solid academic performance is essential for getting good jobs, a better career, and a quality life (Kumar et al., 2021).

There are many factors affecting academic performance, including classroom learning environment, learning resources, family support, delivery of instruction, and study habits. The classroom learning environment is considered one of the essential settings for learners because this is where the learning takes place (Rance et al., 2023). Learning resources are tools that facilitate the process of learning. To lay the groundwork for lifelong learning, teachers must employ appropriate materials. Thus, any educational institution must have sufficient learning resources (Pardillo, 2021). Family support is vital to academic achievement. Supportive and involved parents make children feel valued. Such support inspires the child to work hard and succeed (Llego, 2022).

Meanwhile, the effectiveness of instruction is dependent on the caliber of teachers. They should be well-versed in the areas they are instructing and use technology to enhance the teaching and learning process. Moreover, an individual's study habits are one of the great factors that influence their academic performance and how they perceive achieving success in learning (Magulod, 2017).

In this research setting, the researcher observed that the learners face challenges in achieving academic success due to various factors. These include a lack of classroom space, family support, learning tools, and learners who may not have time to read, study, or do homework. As a result, some learners struggled academically due to their limited access to these essential factors. Therefore, teachers must continue to evaluate students' academic performance.

To address the current concerns, the researcher was motivated to conduct a study assessing the factors affecting learners' academic performance, with the goal of designing a suitable intervention plan that provides learners an opportunity to fill their learning gaps. This is to equip and provide them with the appropriate learning outcomes. Sharpening learners' skills needed to apply in the various contexts while assuring the quality of education in the public elementary schools in a large-sized division in central, Philippines.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to determine the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance in public elementary schools. Specifically, it aimed to determine 1) the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance across five key areas: classroom learning environment, learning resources, family support, delivery of instruction, and study habits; 2) whether there were significant differences in the level of factors affecting learners' performance when grouped and according to the demographic variables.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The success of students in learning is shaped by many influencing factors, be they from inside or outside influence. Some factors come from the students' surroundings, and some from the students' inner drives or preferences, which directly contributed to their academic achievement. According to Suleiman et al. (2024), understanding the key determinants of students' academic performance is paramount for educators, policymakers, and institutions to enhance learning outcomes and facilitate targeted interventions. Cheng et al. (2023) added that an internal factor originates from the individual themselves, independent of external influences, including their abilities. Therefore, internal factors can also have a positive impact and assist students in achieving their goals in the learning process, especially in academic performance. Externally, the external factor comes from outside a person. This factor encompasses the immediate environment, including family and surroundings.

A positive and well-structured classroom learning environment significantly impacts students' academic performance. According to Rymanova & Vlasova (2020), classroom management is an essential determinant of a satisfactory learning environment. The discipline has a lot to do with what teachers expect, secure, and give students' predictability. Disciplinary measures ensure that all students comply with the guidelines set to promote discipline. Other measures include positive reinforcement, student-focused strategies, and cooperative learning. Anhao (2022) reported that the factors affecting learners' academic performance in terms of learning environment issues were moderate. In addition, Anhao's (2022) findings revealed significant differences in the factors affecting learners' academic performance based on their sex, parents' highest educational attainment, and average family income. Specifically, female learners are more attentive in classroom activities than male learners; parents with higher

educational backgrounds provide better educational support; and learners from families with higher incomes have more financial resources for their children's classroom activities.

An adequate learning resources and technology should be provided to ensure effective instruction and engagement. Classrooms should be equipped with various instruction materials, educational resources, and digital learning materials. These are especially important as they meet the needs and preferences of different learners. Moreover, the use of technology in classroom instruction allows students to learn from interactive, enjoyable sessions. Therefore, students can have an engaging learning experience and learn differently from other students at their own pace. Whereas Lastierre, et.,al. (2023) reported that the parental challenges during their children's online learning modality were inadequate learning and technical resources.

Family support are various ways wherein families actively participate in and contribute to a student's learning and academic success. Family support can be indicated by parents' or guardians' interactions with the schools and their children to promote academic success. According to Gündomushi (2018), the lack of parental support for learners also creates a challenge for them to learn and achieve higher grades or performance in all subjects. Students will experience a lack of motivation and support from their parents, which will prevent them from achieving success in their educational endeavors. This is because their parents are the ones who provide them financially, emotionally, and mentally. In addition, Bautista and Carado (2024) concluded that parents who actively participate in various institutional activities demonstrate a deep-seated interest in their child's education and overall welfare.

Delivery of instruction is another important factor affecting academic performance of the learners. According to Guay (2017), educators should encourage children to express their emotions and share their experiences towards learning. Their responses can be used to help teachers redefine their practice and therefore improve the learning experience for all pupils. Learning depends on children's willingness to embrace school life and engage in classroom tasks. Children who respond cooperatively to teachers and perform school-related tasks are among those who show the greatest long-term academic gains. Moreover, according to Srivastava (2022), the academic performance of the learners was significantly influenced by the teachers. They have been given the power to oversee instruction and control all activities in the classroom. The qualities of professionalism and diligence are essential for instructors to have. Hence, they must be approachable, willing to listen, and able to offer answers to the difficulties the students encounter.

Further, study habits influence academic performance. According to Okesina (2019), poor study habits may be influenced by learners' lack of time management skills. Many learners spend their time on activities that may not add up to their academic success and personal development. Yap (2019) revealed that nearly all of the respondents struggle with efficiently and effectively managing their study time. Respondents struggle to adhere to a study schedule, which may lead them to study only when they feel motivated, rather than when it's required.

METHODOLOGY

This portion presents a discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedures for data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive research design to determine the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance in public elementary schools. According to Denzin and Lincoln (2024), descriptive research is not just about documenting facts but about its interpreting and contextualizing them. This involves understanding the "what", where, and when of phenomena, as well as uncovering the deeper meanings behind observed behaviors or interactions. It means that researcher does not manipulate any of the variables but rather only describes the sample and/or the variables (Siedlecki, 2020).

Study Respondents

The study's respondents were the 30 key stage 2 learners. The researcher employed purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their judgment when choosing population members to participate in the study. Purposive sampling allows researchers to access a specific subset of people by selecting all survey participants based on a specific profile (Ames, 2019).

Instrument

This study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire. The researcher made a questionnaire in two parts. The first part comprises the personal Profile of the learners in terms of age, sex, parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income and grade level. The second part of the questionnaire answers the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance. The

level of factors affecting learners' academic performance is split into the areas of classroom learning environment, learning resources, family support, delivery of instruction, and study habits. It is composed of 7 items per area with a total of 35 items. The respondents were asked to rate each item using the five-point Likert scale, which contains the following scores: 5 –Always; 4 –Often; 3 –Sometimes; 2 –Rarely; and 1 –Almost Never. The research instrument was subjected to validity (5.00-excellent) and reliability (0.821-good).

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher asked permission through written communication from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Department of Education of the Division of Negros Oriental, requesting to allow the researcher to distribute the questionnaires to the target respondents. Upon approval of the first request, the researcher provided the school head of the concerned school with a copy of the approved communication from SDS to secure their consent for the study's conduct. After granting permission, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaire to each respondent with the assistance of class advisers. The purpose of the study was properly explained to respondents by the researcher. The questionnaires were administered during the learners' free time not to hamper the schedule of classes. The researcher deliberately read and translated each item on the questionnaire so that the learners could comprehend it fully. Upon the 100% retrieval of the needed data, it was tallied and presented in tabular form for the researcher to interpret and analyze straightforwardly.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and weighted mean to determine the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance in terms of classroom learning environment, learning resources, family support, delivery of instruction, and study habits. Objective No. 2 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U-test to determine the significant difference in the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance when grouped and compared according to demographic profiles.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher prioritized the respondents' voluntary participation, informed consent, risk of harm, confidentiality, and anonymity to prevent any violations of human rights during the research process. Participation in the study was voluntary, and the respondents could withdraw at any time without any consequences. We informed them about the study's academic purpose. Only the researcher(s) had access to the research data, ensuring confidentiality. Moreover, during the study, the researcher strictly observed the governing guidelines and policies of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 to ensure security measures are in place to protect personal and sensitive information. This commitment to ethical standards fostered trust among participants and enhanced the integrity of the research findings. By adhering to these guidelines, we aimed to uphold the highest level of professionalism in our research process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the data gathered were further treated, presented, analyzed, and interpreted to focus on the study's specific objectives.

Table 1

Level of Factors Affecting Learners Academic Performance in the Area of Classroom Learning Environment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a learner, I...</i>		
1. feel safe in the classroom.	4.59	Very High Level
2. feel comfortable participating in class discussions.	4.20	High Level
3. have an inclusive and welcoming classroom environment.	4.46	High Level
4. have an understanding and supportive teacher who motivates me to discover and learn new things.	4.51	Very High Level

5. have a well-organized classroom which is conducive to learning.	4.49	High Level
6. enjoyed learning while performing different tasks and activities provided by the teacher.	4.33	High Level
7. collaborate and share ideas in the class while promoting critical thinking and problem-solving skills.	4.13	High Level
Overall Mean	4.39	High Level

Table 1 presents the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance in the area of classroom learning environment. The respondents obtained an overall mean score of 4.39, interpreted as a high level. Investigating further, respondents assessed the highest mean score of 4.59 on item No. 1, stating, "I feel safe in the classroom," and interpreting it as a very high level. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 4.13 was on item No. 7, stating I collaborate and share ideas in the class while promoting critical thinking and problem-solving skills, and it is interpreted as a high level.

The result implies that almost all learners do feel safe in the classroom. This certainly proves that their safety is the top priority and that they are being nurtured in the learning environment. The school has an immediate action plan in place when danger and other threats to students' safety are seen. This highlights the importance of creating a well-designed physical environment that fosters student engagement, comfort, and improved learning outcomes. The physical setup of the classroom has a significant impact on students' behavior and motivation. Fostering such an atmosphere can ensure that students' welfare and well-being are prioritized, while promoting mastery in lessons and ultimately leading to academic success.

The result aligns with that of Rymanova & Vlasova (2020), who found that classroom management is another essential determinant of a good learning environment. The discipline has a lot to do with what teachers expect, secure, and give students in terms of predictability. The result also aligns with the claims of Mostafa et al. (2023), who found that students from well-lit and ventilated classrooms with flexible settings were generally more focused and participatory.

Table 2

Level of Factors Affecting Learners Academic Performance in the Area of Learning Resources

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a learner, I...</i>		
1. have access to the textbooks I need.	4.16	High Level
2. have a well-equipped classroom with necessary learning resources (e.g., books, materials).	4.30	High Level
3. have a classroom which is well-equipped with technology (e.g., computers, projectors, television, etc.).	3.77	High Level
4. have the textbooks up-to-date and relevant to the curriculum.	3.83	High Level
5. access other learning resources (e.g., libraries, multimedia materials, etc.).	4.19	High Level
6. have access to reliable online applications that help me learn more (e.g., Google, YouTube, etc.).	3.04	Moderate Level
7. have easy access and navigation to online resources.	2.66	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.71	High Level

Table 2 shows the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance in the area of learning resources. The respondents obtained an overall mean score of 3.71, interpreted as a high level. Upon further analysis, the respondents reported the highest mean score of 4.30 for item No. 2, which states, "I have a well-equipped classroom with necessary learning resources," and interpreted this as a high level. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 2.66 was on item No. 7, stating I have simple access and navigation to online resources, which helps us motivate to study, and it is interpreted as a moderate level.

The result suggests that most learners have access to a well-equipped classroom with the necessary learning resources, including books and other materials. This proves that, although the school is located in a remote area, it still has access to the necessary learning resources, thanks to the complex works and countless efforts of specific individuals serving in this school, which shares the common goal of providing a quality education to everyone. Additionally, stakeholders are ensuring that learners have limitless exposure to valuable educational content and resources available in the classroom, potentially advancing their academic growth.

The result aligns with that of Pierro (2020), which suggests that providing adequate learning resources and technology is essential to ensure effective instruction and engagement. Classrooms should be equipped with a variety of instructional materials, educational resources, and digital learning tools to support effective learning and teaching. The result also aligns with claims by Lastierre et al. (2023), who reported that parental challenges during their children's online learning modality included inadequate learning and technical resources.

Table 3

Level of Factors Affecting Learners Academic Performance in the Area of Family Support

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a learner, I...</i>		
1. received help from parents or guardians when faced with difficulty doing homework or school projects.	4.39	High Level
2. have a family who understands the importance of education, encourages me to learn new things, and supports my educational goals.	4.53	Very High Level
3. have a family that provides me with the resources needed (e.g., books, school supplies, etc.).	4.43	High Level
4. become motivated by them to work hard and do my best in school.	4.24	High Level
5. have parents who actively attend school-related activities and events.	3.83	High Level
6. have provided a quiet and comfortable place to study at home.	3.84	High Level
7. have parents who checked and asked for updates regarding my study.	3.91	High Level
Overall Mean	4.17	High Level

Table 3 displays the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance in the area of family support. The respondents obtained an overall mean score of 4.17, interpreted as a high level. Examining the results further, respondents assessed the highest mean score of 4.53 on item No. 2, stating I have a family who understands the importance of education, encourages me to learn new things, and supports my educational goals, and interpreted it as a very high level. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 3.83 was on item No. 5, stating I have parents who actively attend school-related activities and events, and it is interpreted as a high level.

The result suggests that most learners come from families that understand the importance of education, encourage them to learn new things, and support their educational goals. This suggests that most parents are willing to volunteer and support teachers with certain school activities and events because they believe that, as parents, it is their primary responsibility to be

involved with the children's schooling and ensure that their children perform well in school. Although these same parents may not have obtained a higher education themselves, they still recognize the value of education for their children.

The result is supported by Llego (2022); when parents are supportive and involved, the child feels a sense of importance and value. This encourages the child to work hard and to do their best. Parental involvement also provides the child with a role model to follow. Seeing their parents actively involved in their education can inspire the child to do the same. Moreover, Bautista and Carado (2024) concluded that parents who actively participate in various institutional activities demonstrate a deep-seated interest in their child's education and overall welfare.

Table 4

Level of Factors Affecting Learners Academic Performance in the Area of Delivery of Instruction

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a Learner, I ...</i>		
1. clearly understand the teacher's instructions and explanations regarding the topics or lessons.	4.53	Very High Level
2. provided well-illustrated examples and concepts relevant to the discussed topics.	4.44	High Level
3. have been provided with engaging lessons and activities that greatly encourage our participation and collaboration.	4.23	High Level
4. feel comfortable asking for clarifications and can share ideas without judgment.	4.13	High Level
5. could see the teacher's enthusiasm in dealing with the lesson, which adds more positivity in the classroom	4.50	Very High Level
6. enjoyed the applications of technology in delivering the lessons, which enhanced my learning experience.	4.26	High Level
7. observed how strict he/she is when it comes to the rules, but treat all students with fairness	4.26	High Level
Overall Mean	4.33	High Level

Table 4 discloses the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance in the area of delivery of instruction. The respondents obtained an overall mean score of 4.33, interpreted as a high level. Exploring the table further, respondents assessed the highest mean score of 4.53 on item No. 1, stating, "I understand the teacher's instructions and explanations regarding the topics or lessons," and interpreted it as a very high level. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 4.13 was on item No. 4, stating I feel comfortable asking for clarifications and can share ideas without judgment, and it is interpreted as a high level.

The result implies that almost all learners clearly understand the teacher's instructions and explanations regarding the topics or lessons. This is because teachers provide examples and illustrations during discussions to help learners fully grasp what is intended to be achieved. Learners are more focused and engaged in the lesson when they have a clear understanding of what they are learning. For instance, teachers must be well-versed in the areas they are instructing, use technology to enhance the teaching and learning process, implement cutting-edge teaching strategies, maintain classroom order, oversee extracurricular activities, and work in an orderly manner. Additionally, building positive relationships and fostering good communication between learners and teachers ultimately impacts the overall educational experience.

The result aligns with that of Srivastava (2022), indicating that their teachers had a significant influence on the academic performance of learners. They have been given the authority to oversee instruction and manage all classroom activities. The qualities of professionalism and diligence are essential for instructors to have. Hence, they must be approachable, willing to listen, and able to offer answers to the difficulties the students encounter. Moreover, Hattie (2023) asserts that teachers seem to have the most substantial in-school effect, where every child is a learner, is teachable, can grow, and can be taught to love learning. Students have expectations, and the educator’s role is to help students exceed what they think is their potential.

Table 5

Level of Factors Affecting Learners Academic Performance in the Area of Study Habits

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a learner, I ...</i>		
1. make review schedules for examinations.	4.40	High Level
2. submit the given tasks and assignments on time.	4.26	High Level
3. make a list of things to do.	3.74	High Level
4. seek clarification from the teacher to clearly understand what is being discussed.	4.06	High Level
5. study harder to get good grades in every subject, such as from quizzes, assignments, projects, and final exams	4.36	High Level
6. actively participate, share ideas, and participate in group discussion.	4.23	High Level
7. ensure I have organized and destruction-free study areas where I won't be disturbed.	4.03	High Level
Overall Mean	4.15	High Level

Table 5 reveals the level of factors affecting learners’ academic performance in the area of study habits. The respondents obtained an overall mean score of 4.15, interpreted as a high level. Upon further examination of the results, respondents reported the highest mean score of 4.40 for item No. 1, which refers to making review schedules for examinations, and interpreted this as a high level. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 3.74 was on item No. 3, stating I make a list of things to do, and it is interpreted as a high level.

The result implies that mostly learners make review schedules for examinations. Most learners practice the habit of creating review schedules for their upcoming exams. This demonstrates that learners possess proper study habits and effective time management. Most learners consistently practice the habit of studying ahead of time for scheduled examinations, rather than cramming the day before. This tendency to take the exams smoothly indicates an effective preparation strategy, which can lead to higher academic performance and achievements during exams. Developing better study habits and time management skills could significantly enhance their learning outcomes.

The finding relates to Hawthorne (2021), who states that motivation is the force that drives children to achieve higher academic performance, even when they face barriers or challenges. It charges them with the energy required to fulfill their potential. A motivated child is committed, energetic, and innovative; they see the value in what they are learning and are determined to achieve their goals. Those who are intrinsically motivated don’t require sanctions or rewards to help steer their efforts. This form of motivation often encourages more efficient and successful learners in the classroom. In fact, intrinsic motivation is usually shown as one of the most powerful predictors of academic achievement.

Table 6

Difference in the Level of Factors Affecting Learners Academic Performance in the Area of Classroom Learning Environment According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U Test	Kruskal Wallis H test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	32	34.66	581.00		0.749		Not Significant
	Older	38	36.21					
Sex	Male	30	35.52	599.50		0.995		Not Significant
	Female	40	35.49					
Parents Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	48	35.31	519.00		0.909	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	22	35.91					
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	32	34.34	571.00		0.661		Not Significant
	Higher	38	36.47					
Grade Level	Grade 4	27	33.13		1.699	0.428		Not Significant
	Grade 5	23	33.98					
	Grade 6	20	40.45					

Table 6 summarizes the inferential statistics on the difference in the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance in the area of classroom learning environment when grouped and compared according to variables. The computed p-values for variable age, sex, parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and grade level are 0.749, 0.995, 0.909, 0.661, and 0.428, respectively, which are all greater than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis stating there is no significant difference in the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance in the area of classroom learning environment when grouped and compared according to age, sex, parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and grade level was accepted.

The finding implies that the factors affecting learners' academic performance regarding classroom environments do not differ when compared according to age, sex, parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and grade level. This is because most learners, regardless of their background, experienced the same classroom environment. This suggests that the classroom environment has a uniform impact on learners' academic performance, regardless of their demographic differences. Consequently, it highlights the importance of creating an effective learning atmosphere that benefits all learners equally. The result contradicts Anhao's (2023) findings, which revealed significant differences in the factors affecting learners' academic performance based on their sex, parents' highest educational attainment, and average family income. Specifically, female learners are more attentive in classroom activities than male learners; parents with higher educational backgrounds provide better educational support; and learners from families with higher incomes have more financial resources for their children's classroom activities.

Table 7

Difference in the Level of Factors Affecting Learners Academic Performance in the Area of Learning Resources According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U Test	Kruskal Wallis H test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	32	37.16	555.00		0.531	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	38	34.11					
Sex	Male	30	34.07	557.00		0.609	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	40	36.58					
Parents Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	48	34.46	478.00		0.526	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	22	37.77					
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	32	40.30	454.50		0.069	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	38	31.46					
Grade Level	Grade 4	27	29.67		6.735	0.034	0.05	Significant
	Grade 5	23	44.24					
	Grade 6	20	33.33					

Table 7 reviews the inferential statistics on the difference in the level of factors affecting learners’ academic performance in the area of learning resources when grouped and compared according to variables. The computed p-values for variable age, sex, parents’ highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income are 0.531, 0.609, 0.526, and 0.069, respectively, which are all greater than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis stating there is no significant difference in the level of factors affecting learners’ academic performance in the area of learning resources when grouped and compared according to age, sex, parents’ highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income was accepted.

However, for the variable grade level, the computed p-value is 0.034, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as significant. Therefore, the hypothesis stating there is no significant difference in the level of factors affecting learners’ academic performance in the area of learning resources when grouped and compared according to grade level was rejected. This suggests that grade-level comparisons reveal differences in the factors influencing learners' academic performance in the area of learning resources. This is because those learners in the higher grade level have availed themselves of a greater variety of learning resources than those in the lower grade level. As learners progress to higher grade levels, they typically gain access to more advanced and diverse learning resources, which can enhance their academic performance. Consequently, the differences in resource availability contribute to the varying academic outcomes observed between different grade levels. The result relates to that of Pierro (2020): adequate learning resources and technology should be provided to ensure effective instruction and engagement. Classrooms should be equipped with various instruction materials, educational resources, and digital learning materials. These are especially important as they meet the needs and preferences of different learners. Moreover, the use of technology in classroom instruction allows students to learn from interactive, enjoyable sessions. Therefore, students can have an engaging learning experience and learning different students at their own pace.

Table 8

Difference in the Level of Factors Affecting Learners Academic Performance in the Area of Family Support According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U Test	Kruskal Wallis H test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	32	36.34	581.00		0.749		Not Significant
	Older	38	34.79					
Sex	Male	30	34.23	562.00		0.651		Not Significant
	Female	40	36.45					
Parents Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	48	32.71	394.00		0.089	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	22	41.59					
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	32	33.69	550.00		0.492		Not Significant
	Higher	38	37.03					
Grade Level	Grade 4	27	32.46		1.441	0.486		Not Significant
	Grade 5	23	39.35					
	Grade 6	20	35.18					

Table 8 examines the inferential statistics on the difference in the level of factors affecting learners’ academic performance in the area of family support when grouped and compared according to variables.

The computed p-values for variable age, sex, parents’ highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and grade level are 0.749, 0.651, 0.089, 0.492, and 0.486, respectively, which are all greater than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis stating there is no significant difference in the level of factors affecting learners’ academic performance in the area of family support when grouped and compared according to age, sex, parents’ highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and grade level was accepted.

The results suggest that the factors influencing learners’ academic performance related to family support are consistent across different categories, including age, sex, parents’ highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and grade level. Most of the learners observed the same situation in their respective families, wherein they received minimal support from their family towards school-related activities and events. This indicates that regardless of varying backgrounds and circumstances, many learners experience a lack of family involvement in their education. Consequently, this minimal support may negatively impact their overall academic success. The result is supported by Gündomushi (2018); the lack of parental support for learners also creates a challenge for them to learn and achieve higher grades or performance in all subjects. Students will experience a lack of motivation and support from their parents, which will prevent them from achieving success in their educational endeavors.

Table 9

Difference in the Level of Factors Affecting Learners Academic Performance in the Area of Delivery of Instruction According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U Test	Kruskal Wallis H test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
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Age	Younger	32	32.56	514.00	0.265	Not Significant
	Older	38	37.97			
Sex	Male	30	36.43	572.00	0.738	Not Significant
	Female	40	34.80			
Parents Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	48	35.02	505.00	0.770	Not Significant
	Higher	22	36.55			
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	32	34.86	587.50	0.808	Not Significant
	Higher	38	36.04			
Grade Level	Grade 4	27	30.54	2.663	0.264	Not Significant
	Grade 5	23	38.24			
	Grade 6	20	39.05			

Table 9 shows the inferential statistics on the difference in the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance in the area of delivery of instruction when grouped and compared according to variables. The computed p-values for variable age, sex, parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and grade level are 0.265, 0.738, 0.770, 0.808, and 0.264, respectively, which are all greater than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis stating there is no significant difference in the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance in the area of delivery of instruction when grouped and compared according to age, sex, parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and grade level was accepted.

The result implies that the factors affecting learners' academic performance related to delivery of instruction do not vary when compared according to age, sex, parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and grade level. Most of the learners observed that the teachers deliver classroom instruction effectively, show enthusiasm in delivering instructions, and deal fairly with all types of learners. This suggests that regardless of demographic differences, learners perceive the quality of instruction as consistent and positive. Therefore, effective teaching practices seem to transcend individual backgrounds and contribute to a uniform academic experience. According to Srivastava (2022), the academic performance of the learners was significantly influenced by the teachers. They have been given the power to oversee instruction and control all activities in the classroom. The qualities of professionalism and diligence are essential for instructors to have. Hence, they must be approachable, willing to listen, and able to offer answers to the difficulties the students encounter.

Table 10

Difference in the Level of Factors Affecting Learners Academic Performance in the Area of Study Habits According to Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean	Mann-Whitney U Test	Kruskal Wallis H test	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	32	33.05	529.50		0.353	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	38	37.57					
Sex	Male	30	35.70	594.00		0.943		Not Significant

	Female	40	35.35			
Parents Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	48	33.65	439.00	0.258	Not Significant
	Higher	22	39.55			
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	32	32.56	514.00	0.266	Not Significant
	Higher	38	37.97			
Grade Level	Grade 4	27	30.26	5.048	0.080	Not Significant
	Grade 5	23	42.98			
	Grade 6	20	33.98			

Table 10 displays the inferential statistics on the difference in the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance in the area of study habits when grouped and compared according to variables. The computed p-values for variable age, sex, parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and grade level are 0.353, 0.943, 0.258, 0.266, and 0.080, respectively, which are all greater than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis stating there is no significant difference in the level of factors affecting learners' academic performance in the area of study habits when grouped and compared according to age, sex, parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and grade level was accepted.

The finding implies that the factors affecting learners' academic performance in terms of study habits do not differ when compared according to age, sex, parents' highest educational attainment, average family monthly income, and grade level. This situation happened because most of the learners have the same study habits irrespective of their backgrounds. Most of the learners don't have proper or regular study time or schedules, as most of them prefer to study a day or night before the exams or quizzes. This approach often leads to increased stress and lower retention of information. Consequently, teachers may need to implement strategies that encourage consistent study routines and effective time management skills among learners. According to Okesina (2019), poor study habits may be influenced by learners' lack of time management skills. Many learners allocate their time to activities that may not contribute to their academic success and personal development.

CONCLUSION

The high level of factors that contributed to learners' academic performance were due to a good classroom environment, adequate learning resources, a supportive family, competent teachers, and good study habits. The learners observed the same perception of the factors affecting their academic performance regardless of their background. Further, the grade level of a learner is a predicting factor for academic performance with respect to learning resources, indicating as learners progress to higher levels, they typically need access to more advanced and diverse learning resources, which can enhance their academic performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on these results, the study recommends to calls for school heads, teachers, and parents to work together to provide the learners the materials and support they need for their successful educational journey.

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Conflict of Interest

We maintain that none of the authors of this paper have a financial obligation or personal relationship with any person(s) or organizations that could inappropriately influence/bias the paper's content. We do not receive funding from any person(s) or organization to carry out this research. Given this, we specifically state that "No Competing interests are at stake and there is No Conflict of Interest" with any person(s) or organizations that could inappropriately influence/bias the content of the paper.

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